
Levels of Development in Drought Prone Area of Eastern Sangli District (Maharashtra): A Geographical Perspective

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15063400

Introduction:

One of the most common climatic and natural disasters worldwide is drought. Droughts, which can afflict the majority of society and have severe effects on the economy, can linger for months or even years. A drought is a transient, recurrent natural calamity that results from insufficient precipitation and causes large-scale financial losses. It evokes a mood of gloom and hopelessness. Drought can be attributed to water scarcity as both a cause and an effect. Anytime one of the hydrological cycle's linkages breaks or becomes unstable, drought results. Drought is a poison; nobody can anticipate when it will strike, how long it will persist, or how severe it will be.

Due to its wide spatial scope, it may significantly affect the socioeconomic stability of a whole region. There is no way to prevent droughts. However, strategies for preparing for and managing the effects of drought are attainable. The effectiveness of both is dependent, among other things, on the degree to which droughts are identified and their features are measured (Smakhtin et al., 2004). With over 70% of its people reliant on agriculture, India is primarily an agrarian nation. More than 68% of the nation's net sown area is drought prone due to the unpredictable nature of rainfall, of which 50% is severe. Every two to three

years, there is a drought in one or more regions of the nation.

Any area's capacity to develop depends on its climate, which is also influenced by geographic features and other human variables. Development can be defined as the qualitative improvement of the preceding state or as a shift in the desired direction at the desired speed. The eastern portion of Sangli district is considered a drought-prone area because of the main issue of water shortage brought on by the lack of rainfall; as a result, these types of locations lag behind in terms of development and require further research.

Study Area:

The development levels in the eastern portion of the Sangli district are the main subject of this study. The Sangli district is bordered by the states of Maharashtra and Karnataka and is situated in the far south of the state. The district is bordered to the north by the districts of Satara and Solapur, to the west by the districts of Ratnagiri and Kolhapur, and to the north by the districts of Belgaum and Bijapur in Karnataka. As a result, the district has two distinct cultures. The district, which covers an area of 8591.3 kilometers, is divided into 10 tehsils. The district is separated geographically into three zones: the eastern, central, and western zones. The

eastern zone's study region includes the tehsils of Jat, Kavathe-Mahankal, and Atpadi. Total area of study region is 3792.4 kilometer.

Objectives:

To Find Out Levels of Development in Study Area.

Database and Methodology:

Primary Data:

Both primary and secondary sources of data were used to create the current study. The six study region villages that were chosen for the field survey used a household schedule, and the interview approach was evaluated. The primary data were gathered in this way.

Secondary Data:

The secondary data collected from a variety of sources, including dissertations, books, journals, articles, socioeconomic reviews, the primary census abstract of Maharashtra state from 2001 to 2011, the census reports published by the Indian government in 2001 and 2011, the Socio-economic Review, and the district statistical abstract of Sangli district.

Methodology:

The study primarily uses data from primary and secondary sources to achieve this goal. Primary data were obtained through extensive fieldwork in six chosen villages located in the eastern region of Maharashtra's Sangli district. Three sample villages are chosen from the rural areas of the tehsils, while three sample villages are chosen close to the tehsil headquarters. In all, 120 homes in the sample villages were surveyed. It has aided in our comprehension of the study region's overall growth. However, secondary data have also been used to examine their overall development in the research area as well as their distribution pattern, growth rate, literacy status, and occupational structure. The basic data was collected using a systematic sampling technique, with every third house being evaluated for data collection.

Tehsil and village levels of development were also measured. The socio-economic development of villages, tehsils, and the 2011 and 2001 censuses was based on data from systematic sample surveys conducted between 2017 and 2018. The five socioeconomic indicators of literacy rate, female literacy rate, labor participation rate, percentage of workers in the non-agricultural sector, and sex ratio (i.e., number of females per 1000 male population) are the basis for the composite indexes of development for the tehsil level for the years 2001 and 2011.

The next twelve socioeconomic indicators for the development of villages at the village level include the percentage of people employed in the non-agricultural sector, female literacy, and literacy rate. income per capita (in rupees), Share of households with three or more rooms; percentage of households with two wheels; percentage of households with radios and tape recorders; percentage of households with televisions; percentage of households with pooled and RCC houses; and

percentage of households with latrines. Composite indices are employed in the development process computation.

Data Analysis:

Levels of Development (2001):

The eastern portion of Sangli district, which includes the tehsils of Jat, Kavathe-Mahankal, and Atpadi, is classified as a drought-prone area due to little rainfall and high temperatures, according to the 2001 census. In comparison, three tehsils within the research region had a highly developed Kavathe-Mahankal tehsil. The primary cause of this was the implementation of several irrigation projects, which improved the non-agricultural sector's workforce base, literacy rate, and work participation ratio while also leaving some areas of the Kavathe-Mahankal tehsil in decent condition. Every four to five years, Atpadi Tehsil also experiences a drought because the tehsil is located in a rain shadow area, which results in less rainfall there. This tehsil's sex ratio and literacy rate were both high, but its low labor force participation rate and low number of workers in the non-agricultural sector meant that this indicator lagged behind in the development category. When compared to Atpadi and Kavathe-Mahankal tehsils in the eastern portion of Sangli district, Jat tehsil—which is the largest tehsil in the district based on area—is lagging behind in terms of development. The Jat tehsil is situated in the eastern section of the district. Its horizontal shape means that its climate is similar throughout, with frequent high temperatures and little precipitation.

The Jat tehsils work participation rate and percentage of workers in the non-agricultural sector were extremely low, which led to extremely low levels of development in this tehsil. The Kavathe-Mahankal tehsil had an average composite score of 5.09, Atpadi 4.82, while Jat tehsil had an index value of 4.52. The eastern

portion of the Sangli district has an average composite value of 4.81, indicating extremely regressive growth in this area.

Table 1: Levels of Development, 2001

Sr. No.	Tehsil	Composite Index
1	Kavathe-Mahankal	5.09
2	Atpadi	4.82
3	Jat	4.52
	Average	4.81

Source: Census of India 2001, & District Census Handbook, Sangli District.

Levels of Development (2011):

In comparison, Kavathe-Mahankal tehsil in the eastern portion of Sangli district was highly developed according to the 2011 census. After that, Atpadi tehsil came and Jat tehsil remained backward, same as the 2001 census, in three tehsils in the study region. Due to irrigation projects, agricultural development has been noticed in Kavathe-Mahankal tehsil over the past 56 years. This tehsil is in better shape because the work participation rate, literacy rate, and number of workers in the non-agricultural sector have all increased during the past ten years. The state of development in Atpadi Tehsil likewise improves, although the percentage of workers who are not in the agricultural sector and their labor force participation rate decline.

Table 2: Levels of Development, 2011

Sr. No.	Tehsil	Composite Index
1	Kavathe-Mahankal	5.29
2	Atpadi	5.27
3	Jat	4.79
	Average	5.12

Source: Census of India 2011, & District Census Handbook, Sangli District

This tehsils sex ratio and literacy rate both increased, but the percentage of workers in the non-agricultural sector and labor participation rate decreased. As a result, this indicator lagged behind and stayed in the same place in the development category. In comparison to the results of Kavathe-Mahankal and Atpadi tehsils, the Jat tehsils levels of development were relatively low. This was evident in the labor participation rate and the low percentage of female literacy among non-agricultural sector workers. Kavathe-Mahankal tehsils average composite values were 5.29, Atpadi tehsils 5.27, and Jat tehsils 4.79 index values. In comparison to other Sangli district regions, the eastern section of the district has very sluggish development, as seen by the average composite value of 5.12 obtained from the 2011 census. According to the 2011

census, Atpadi and Kavathe-Mahankal tehsils are classified as underdeveloped, whereas Jat tehsil is classified as backwardly developed. The map displays the composite index for the top five and below five.

Levels of Development in Sample Villages (2017-18):

Kokale village in Kawathe-Mahankal tehsil, which has the most development in the sample villages of the eastern portion of Sangli district, has a composite value of 14.08, while Madgule village in Atpadi tehsil has the lowest composite index, at 11.09. Madgule village was found to be weaker than all other sample villages because the majority of the villagers live in kutchha and semi-pucca houses, there are very few household assets, few households are reported to be homeless, and there is little to no agricultural development. However, Kokale village in Kavathe-Mahankal tehsil has the highest levels of development that have been observed. This is because the village is located near a main road, water is available, agricultural development is in a good stage, the work participation rate is high and the majority of the population uses government services, indicating that the economic situation is good.

As a result, the composite value of Kokale village is 14.08 higher than that of the other sample villages. Dafalapur in Jat tehsil has a composite index of 13.21, followed by Walekhindi at 13.13, Shiradhon at 12.26, Awalai at 11.68, and Madgule in Atpadi tehsil at 11.09. These values indicate that the region as a whole is experiencing the same drought issue because the variation between the six villages is not maximum. According to the field study, Kavathe-Mahankal tehsil has the highest level of development, followed by Jat tehsil, which is in the middle category, and Atpadi tehsil, which has the lowest levels of development.

Table 3: Levels of Development in Sample Villages, 2017-18

Sr. No.	Village	Tehsil	Composite Index
1	Dafalapur	Jat	13.21
2	Walekhindi	Jat	13.13
3	Shiradhon	Kavathe-Mahankal	12.26
4	Kokale	Kavathe-Mahankal	14.08
5	Madgule	Atpadi	11.09
6	Awalai	Atpadi	11.68
Average			12.57

Source: Fieldwork 2017-18.

Conclusions:

The above said data clearly shows the degrees of development according to the 2001 census, with Kavathe-Mahankal tehsil having the highest levels of development, followed by Atpadi tehsil and Jat tehsil being classified as having backward development. The research region's development levels have not changed in ten years; only the numbers have. The primary factor influencing development levels is the drought; this is also demonstrated by the data, which show that the development is significantly impacted by the work participation rate and the number of workers in the non-agricultural sector. The data clearly show where the work participation ratio was good that places with the best levels of growth and development.

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